

Ruthenium(VIII) catalysed Oxidation of some Organic Substrates

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Manuscript received 6 June 1993, revised 16 August 1993, accepted 17 September 1993

Ruthenium(VIII) oxide catalysed oxidation of methanol, ethanol, hexylene glycol, glycerol, diethylene glycol and triethylene glycol by aqueous alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) shows zero order kinetics in [oxidant] and inverse proportionality in $[\text{OH}^-]$. Reaction throughout shows first order with respect to [Hexylene glycol] and [Glycerol] while in case of the remaining four substrates, after showing first order kinetics initially the reaction becomes independent with respect to methanol, ethanol, diethylene glycol and triethylene glycol at their higher concentrations. An outer sphere mechanism via hydride ion transfer has been proposed.

Ruthenium(III) chloride catalysed oxidation of organic compounds by hexacyanoferrate(III)^{1,2} in alkaline and cerium(IV) sulphate³ in acidic medium⁴ has been extensively studied. Ruthenium(VIII) oxide has been reported to break the double bond in unsaturated organic compounds⁵. Recently, its catalytic activity was reported in alkaline⁶ and acidic media⁷ from our laboratory. But the oxidation of aforesaid organic compounds has not yet been studied. Hence in order to examine the exact catalytic nature of ruthenium(VIII) oxide, the present kinetic data have been collected and probable reaction path of the reaction has been proposed.

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of methanol, ethanol, hexylene glycol, glycerol, diethylene glycol and triethylene glycol (referred to as Met, Et, HG, Gly, DEG and TEG respectively) by aqueous alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ion catalysed by ruthenium(VIII) oxide has been studied under the conditions where uncatalysed reaction is negligible. Rate of the reaction has been calculated in terms of the initial $-dc/dt$ values obtained from the individual zero order plots of remaining [oxidant] vs time. Although the addition of KCl does not effect the reaction velocity even then the ionic strength of the medium was kept constant.

Concentrations mentioned in the tables are the initial concentrations of the reactants.

Typical zero order plots and practically constant zero order rate values (Table 1) clearly indicate zero order kinetics with respect to [oxidant]. A slight increase in the rate values at higher hexacyanoferrate(III) concentrations might be due to the further oxidation of the intermediate products via the un-catalysed route and the acid produced during the course of the reaction. It has been shown that intermediate product is further oxidised only by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) and not by the catalyst⁸. Moreover, ruthenium is incapable of oxidising aldehydes and ketones having no hydride ion. Linear increase in rate values with increasing [Catalyst] and constant k values (where $k = (-dc/dt)/[\text{RuO}_4]$) for molar concentration of RuO_4 , shows first order kinetics with respect to catalyst concentrations in all the cases (Table 2). The plots of substrate concentration vs rate indicate first order kinetics with respect to [HG] and [Gly], while in case of the remaining four organic substrates after showing first order kinetics initially the rate becomes independent with respect to [Met], [Et], [DEG] and [TEG]. Difference in the nature shown by HG and Gly might be due to the fact that experimental conditions inhibited the study at still higher concentrations of these two

organic substrates where one might observe the same independent nature of the reaction with respect to [HG] and [Gly] also. Steady decrease in $-dc/dt$ values with increasing $[\text{OH}^-]$ and straight lines with positive intercepts on plotting $1/\text{rate}$, vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ in case of Met, Et, DEG and TEG, show that the rate of the reaction is inversely proportional with respect to $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Table 3).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)] ON REACTION RATE

Compd.	[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] $\times 10^3 M$		Mean $-dc/dt \times 10^4$ (\bar{X})	Standard deviation (σ_{n-1})
	From	To		
Methanol	1.25	8.00	1.04	0.059
Ethanol	1.25	8.00	0.81	0.064
Hexylene glycol	1.25	8.00	0.29	0.063
Glycerol	1.25	10.00	0.18	0.026
Diethylene glycol	1.00	8.00	0.88	0.054
Triethylene glycol	1.00	5.00	0.60	0.034

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[\text{RuO}_4]$ ON THE REACTION RATE AT 35°

$[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ (for A, B, C, E and F)
 $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ (for D)

(A) [Methanol] = $20.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 1.00 M$
 (B) [Ethanol] = $10.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 1.00 M$
 (C) [Hexylene glycol] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-1} M$
 (D) [Glycerol] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-1} M$
 (E) [Diethylene glycol] = $2.50 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$
 (F) [Triethylene glycol] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$

$[\text{RuO}_4] \times 10^6 M$	$k_A \times 10^{-2}$	$k_B \times 10^{-2}$	k_C	$k_D \times 10^{-2}$	$k_E \times 10^{-2}$	$k_F \times 10^{-2}$
0.06	—	0.198	—	—	—	—
0.12	—	0.181	—	—	—	0.18
0.18	—	0.187	—	—	—	—
0.24	—	0.173	—	—	0.12	0.17
0.30	0.092	0.165	—	—	—	—
0.36	—	0.176	—	—	0.12	0.18
0.48	0.066	0.177	—	—	0.12	0.17
0.60	0.069	0.158	—	—	0.12	0.16
0.91	—	—	—	—	0.11	0.15
1.09	—	—	—	—	0.11	0.14
1.21	0.064	—	—	1.51	0.11	0.15
1.81	0.62	—	—	1.65	—	—
2.42	0.051	—	2.02	1.34	—	—
3.025	0.60	—	—	1.37	—	—
4.84	—	—	2.20	1.42	—	—
6.05	—	—	2.40	1.42	—	—
9.08	—	—	2.27	1.33	—	—
12.10	—	—	2.42	1.34	—	—
15.125	—	—	2.33	—	—	—

where $k = (-dc/dt)/[\text{RuO}_4]$

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[\text{OH}^-]$ ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

$[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ for A, B, C, E and F; $5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ for D
 (A) [Methanol] = $0.08 M$, $[\text{RuO}_4] = 6.050 \times 10^{-6} M$
 (B) [Ethanol] = $0.20 M$, $[\text{RuO}_4] = 3.025 \times 10^{-6} M$
 (C) [Hexylene glycol] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{RuO}_4] = 3.005 \times 10^{-5} M$
 (D) [Glycerol] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{RuO}_4] = 3.025 \times 10^{-5} M$
 (E) [Diethylene glycol] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{RuO}_4] = 06.05 \times 10^{-6} M$
 (F) [Triethylene glycol] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{RuO}_4] = 3.025 \times 10^{-6} M$

$[\text{NaOH}]$ $\times 10^2 M$	$-dc/dt \times 10^4 M \text{ min}^{-1}$					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
0.40	—	—	—	—	1.14	—
0.50	—	—	—	—	1.05	1.14
0.60	—	—	—	—	—	1.05
0.70	—	—	—	—	0.98	—
0.90	—	—	—	—	0.95	—
1.00	—	3.25	—	—	—	0.96
1.20	—	—	—	—	0.86	—
1.50	—	—	—	—	—	0.90
2.00	—	2.00	—	—	—	0.78
2.80	—	—	—	—	0.62	—
3.00	—	1.60	—	—	—	—
3.80	—	—	—	—	0.50	—
4.00	—	—	—	—	—	0.55
5.00	—	1.25	0.55	—	—	—
5.80	—	—	—	—	0.40	—
6.00	—	1.00	—	—	—	0.38
7.50	—	—	0.40	—	—	—
8.00	—	0.82	—	—	—	0.30
10.00	0.49	0.74	0.36	0.032	0.28	0.28
20.00	0.44	—	0.22	0.026	—	—
30.00	0.42	—	0.18	0.024	—	—
40.00	0.40	—	0.14	0.020	—	—
50.00	0.38	—	0.08	0.014	—	—
60.00	0.36	—	—	0.011	—	—
80.00	0.35	—	—	—	—	—
100.00	0.34	—	—	—	—	—

Stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by taking hexacyanoferrate(III) in large excess as compared to the organic substrate in different ratios and the observations were made for a long period. The estimation of unconsumed hexacyanoferrate(III) by the usual method gives following stoichiometric equation,

Paper chromatographic technique and spot test methods⁹ confirmed formic, acetic and oxalic acids and the corresponding dicarboxylic acids as the final oxidation products in case of Met, Et, DEG, TEG, HG and Gly respectively.

Electronic spectral studies¹⁰⁻¹² confirmed that $\text{RuO}_4(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$ is the only reactive and stable species of RuO_4 in alkaline media,

The spectrum of the orange solution of potassium ruthenate in 1.0 M NaOH (the solution is stable for more than a year) revealed the molar extinction coefficient corresponding to the two absorption maxima at 385 and 460 nm. This indicates the presence of species RuO_4^- and RuO_4^{2-} . Moreover, the standard solution of hexacyanoferrate(III) immediately decolorises the known amount of ruthenium tetroxide solution and the molar extinction coefficient of this solution corresponds to absorption maxima at 305–310 nm indicating the presence of RuO_4 . Similar spectra at similar absorption maxima have been reported by Connick and Hurley¹⁰ for ruthenium(VIII) species. All these evidences along with electronic spectral studies confirm that the reduced form of ruthenium is again oxidised to its original octavalent state by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) and it may be assumed that RuO_4 in alkaline medium will remain as $\text{RuO}_4(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$ and only this form will act as homogeneous catalyst. Moreover, previous workers have reported hydride ion transfer from α -carbon atom of the organic molecules.

On the basis of the above facts the following scheme for the oxidation of aforesaid organic substrates may be presented,

Here R represents the corresponding part of the organic substrate.

Considering the steady state condition for [Complex] the final rate law in terms of decreasing concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(III) will be given as

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1k_2[\text{S}][\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}}{k_2 + k_{-1}[\text{OH}^-] + k_1[\text{S}]} \quad (4)$$

At low [S] and comparatively higher $[\text{OH}^-]$, the approximation $k_{-1}[\text{OH}^-] \gg k_2 + k_1[\text{S}]$ might be assumed depending upon the values of k_2 and k_1 and hence equation (4) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2Kk_2[\text{S}][\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (5)$$

where $K = k_1/k_{-1}$. Equation (5) clearly explains all the experimental findings in case of HG and Gly. It also explains the reason for the first order kinetics with respect to organic substrate concentrations. With the help of equation (5), from the plots of rate vs [S], rate vs $[\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}$ and rate vs $1/[\text{OH}^-]$, the Kk_2 values were calculated (Table 4). Constancy in Kk_2 values confirms the validity of rate law and the mechanism.

Now to verify rate law (4) in case of Met, Et, DEG and TEG, it can be rewritten as

$$1/\text{Rate} = \frac{1}{2k_1[\text{S}][\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}} + \frac{1}{2k_2[\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}} + \frac{k_{-1}[\text{OH}^-]}{2k_1k_2[\text{S}][\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_{\text{T}}} \quad (6)$$

TABLE 4

Compd.	Plot	Kk_2	k_2	K
Methanol	1/rate vs $[\text{OH}^-]$	88.0		20.0
		86.0		
Ethanol	1/rate vs $1/[\text{S}]$	-	4.4	-
	1/rate vs $[\text{OH}^-]$	7.10	-	0.77
Hexylene glycol	1/rate vs $1/[\text{S}]$	-	9.2	-
	Rate vs $[\text{S}]$	10.99	-	-
Glycerol	Rate vs $[\text{RuO}_4]$	10.41	-	-
	Rate vs $1/[\text{OH}^-]$	9.72	-	-
Diethylene glycol	Rate vs $[\text{S}]$	11.41	-	-
	Rate vs $[\text{RuO}_4]$	14.63	-	-
Triethylene glycol	Rate vs $1/[\text{OH}^-]$	11.15	-	-
	1/rate vs $[\text{OH}^-]$	15.23	-	-
Triethylene glycol	1/rate vs $1/[\text{S}]$	14.92	-	0.72
			21.75	0.69
Triethylene glycol	1/rate vs $[\text{OH}^-]$	29.84	-	0.58
	1/rate vs $1/[\text{S}]$		51.65	-

From equation (6), by plotting graphs between $1/\text{Rate}$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $1/\text{Rate}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$, the Kk_2 and k_2 values were calculated from the slopes and intercepts respectively (Table 4). An examination of K values, calculated from the Kk_2 and k_2 values, shows that the rate of formation of complex between ruthenium(viii) and organic substrate is inversely proportional to the size of the substrate molecule, the K values being maximum for Met and minimum for TEG; while the rate of disproportion (k_2) is proportional to the size of organic molecule, k_2 being minimum for Met and maximum for TEG. Theoretically also due to steric effect, a small ligand like Met is easily accommodated around the central metal ion while in case of the complex formed with larger molecule like TEG the complex is relatively more hindered sterically. Practically constant Kk_2 and k_2 from two different graphs at two different concentrations finally confirm the validity of rate law (5) and hence the proposed mechanism.

Experimental

Hexacyanoferrate(III), (AnalaR) methanol, ethanol and glycerol (E. Merck), diethylene glycol, triethylene glycol and hexylene glycol (Raidel) solutions were prepared by weight in deoxygenated

double-distilled water. Solution of ruthenium tetroxide (Johnson Matthey) was prepared in NaOH. The final strengths of the catalyst and alkali were $3.025 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $0.135 M$ respectively. Progress of the reaction was measured at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$), by following the decrease in absorbance of the reaction mixture at 420 nm on a Beckman 26 spectrophotometer. As the Beer's law is obeyed in the entire concentration range of hexacyanoferrate(III) ion, its concentration was calculated from a calibration curve.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.K.T.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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